

LA-UR-03-2154

Approved for public release;
distribution is unlimited.

Title:

Nanocompressive Properties of Carbon Microballoons
and Mechanical Properties of Carbon Based Syntactic
Foam Composites

Author(s):

K. Carlisle, K.K. Chawla, G. Gouadec, M. Koopman,
and G.M. Gladysz

Submitted to:

14th International Conference on Composite Materials
(ICCM-14) to be held July 14-18, 2003 in San Diego,
California, U.S.A

Los Alamos National Laboratory, an affirmative action/equal opportunity employer, is operated by the University of California for the U.S. Department of Energy under contract W-7405-ENG-36. By acceptance of this article, the publisher recognizes that the U.S. Government retains a nonexclusive, royalty-free license to publish or reproduce the published form of this contribution, or to allow others to do so, for U.S. Government purposes. Los Alamos National Laboratory requests that the publisher identify this article as work performed under the auspices of the U.S. Department of Energy. Los Alamos National Laboratory strongly supports academic freedom and a researcher's right to publish; as an institution, however, the Laboratory does not endorse the viewpoint of a publication or guarantee its technical correctness.

Nanocompressive Properties of Carbon Microballoons and Mechanical Properties of Carbon Based Syntactic Foam Composites

K. Carlisle¹, K.K. Chawla¹, G. Gouadec¹, M. Koopman¹, and G.M. Gladysz²

¹*Department of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Alabama at Birmingham, 1530 Third Ave. South, BEC 254, Birmingham, AL USA 35294-4461*

²*Los Alamos National Laboratory, Engineering Sciences & Applications Division, Weapon Materials & Manufacturing, MS C930, Los Alamos, NM USA 87545*

ABSTRACT

A novel technique for compressive testing of individual carbon microballoons, CMB, has been developed, utilizing a specially equipped nanoindentation apparatus. The CMB range in size from 10 to 100 μm and are an integral component in carbon based syntactic foams.

Polished cross sections of the foams and electron microscopy revealed complicated structures in many of the CMB, rather than simple hollow spheres. Stereological techniques were used to evaluate variations in CMB wall thickness.

Because syntactic foam composites have low density, approximately 0.3 g/cm^3 , they have a wide range of applications and potential applications in aerospace and other transportation fields. The foam composites consist of CMB, bismaleimide resin and voids. Cylinders of syntactic foams were tested in compression. Unconfined compression strength was between 4.5 and 7 MPa. The stress-strain curves showed an elastic region followed by a plateau at or near the ultimate compressive strength and then failure of the sample by exfoliating flakes from the edges of the cylinders. Dynamic modulus measurements were performed by impulse excitation and the dynamic flexural modulus was approximately 737 MPa.

Key Terms: syntactic foams, carbon, microballoons, compression, and nanocompression.

I. INTRODUCTION

Syntactic foams are composite cellular materials but are not formed via traditional blowing techniques. Rather, they are constructed by dispersing hollow spheres in a binder phase. The presence of “cells” is due to the fact that the reinforcing particles are hollow. The hollow particles are formed in an earlier blowing process, the details of which are beyond the scope of this paper. The end product is a two-phase composite composed of a suitable matrix material reinforced with hollow spheres.

Composites of this nature are used in transportation and aerospace applications, where weight reduction heavily influences all aspects of design. A classic example of a syntactic foam use is the sandwich composite beam. The syntactic foam composes the beam core, where it provides a foundation for bonding the skin of the beam, usually a fiber composite. Here, the key properties of the syntactic foam are its low weight, compressive strength, and ability to form a strong bond with the skin. These structures are then used to replace various metallic channeled beams, affording designers significant weight reductions with no strength penalties. Similar construction tactics also make syntactic foam sandwich construction an attractive option in submersibles, where compressive strength is a high priority to withstand the loading of deep-sea operations [1- 4].

Carbon microballoons (CMB)—see Figure 1—are a somewhat less common reinforcement than the typical glass microballoons. This is due to several factors, ranging from the increased cost of CMB to the greater difficulty involved in their production. In spite of these disadvantages, CMB are possible replacement materials for glass microballoons in syntactic foams when lighter reinforcements and /or better thermal conductivity are desired. Additionally, CMB can be found in syntactic foams of a totally different nature. These are the three-phase foams, as are studied here. In this particular case, the CMB are bound together by an APO-BMI resin matrix that does not completely fill the space between the balloons; instead, it merely coats the CMB surfaces, and “bridges” adjacent CMBs. The three-phase microstructure thus created contains CMB, a thermosetting polymer binder, and interstitial voids between the balloons, as can be seen in Figure 2. Note that the structure as seen in the figure has been modified by the vacuum impregnation mounting technique: open voids in the real structure are represented here by the regions filled with mounting resin [5].

Figure 1: SEM micrograph of an individual CMB

Figure 2: Polished CMB foam showing CMB & binder phases. Voids in the actual structure are filled with mounting resin. Note imperfections in the form of broken and nested CMB within the foam.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Nanocompression

The nanocompression test around which much of this research centers is a new test method that has been developed at UAB that extends the use of traditional engineering compression testing to samples as small as a few micrometers in size. The technique involves the modification of a Nanoindenter XP II, produced by MTS. This instrument has proven ideal, since it measures load and displacement data with resolutions of 50 nN and 0.02 nm, respectively. The Berkovich indenter tip is

replaced with a specially fabricated, single crystal cylindrical sapphire punch. This tip, when combined with a mounted and polished 6061 T6 aluminum stub placed in the motorized sample stage of the nanoindenter, converts the nanoindenter into a compression test frame, capable of testing CMB whose contact area with the tip is less than the surface area of the sapphire tip— 0.0249 mm^2 . Figure 3 provides a schematic of the nanocompression test apparatus, including the microscope objective that is integrated into the system.

Figure 3: Schematic of nanocompression apparatus, showing sapphire tip and 40x objective lens.

Before changing the indenter tip, the Berkovich tip is used to indent fused silica, an accepted standard that ensures correct calibration of the instrument for hardness and modulus as a function of depth into the sample. Once calibrated, the modifications described above are made and the actual test begins with the careful distribution of CMB on the aluminum alloy substrate, which serves as the lower platen for the compression test. A pre-compression optical micrograph of each target CMB is taken, from which measurements of the balloon's optical diameter are taken. This optical diameter is an average of two perpendicular measurements taken from each image. After a number of CMB are selected, the test parameters—approach speed and load limit—are selected by the operator—usually 50 nm/s and 100 mN for CMB testing [6, 7].

2.2 Quantitative microscopy of polished CMB foams

The samples were mounted via resin-impregnation and polished using a specially developed procedure. This procedure involved grinding on 500, 1200, and 4000 grit SiC papers with H_2O lubricant, followed by a $3 \mu\text{m}$ diamond polish, and finished with a $0.01 \mu\text{m}$ Al_2O_3 chemical polish.

After polishing, the samples were imaged with a Zeiss Axioplane Microscope at a magnification of 500 X, at which the wall thicknesses were adequately resolved. These images were then processed in Image Pro Plus—a commercially available image analysis program. The area fraction (A_A) of the CMB walls and the points per line length (P_L) of the CMB walls were measured with a set of concentric circular test lines. The A_A and P_L measurements were output to a text file which could be opened and manipulated in Excel to obtain the average mean lineal intercept of the CMB walls, $\bar{\lambda}_w$, according to the following equation:

$$\bar{\lambda}_w = \frac{4A_A}{2P_L}$$

The average true thickness of the CMB walls was obtained from the $\bar{\lambda}_w$ and the diameter data from nanocompression testing, which revealed that the average diameter of the CMB was between 22

and 23 μm . This was done by considering the following derived equation, which assumes that the CMB are spherical shells:

$$\bar{\lambda}_{wall} = \frac{4t(t^2 - 1.5t\phi + 0.75\phi^2)}{3(t^2 - t\phi + 0.5\phi^2)}$$

2.3 Compression testing

Unconfined compression testing of cylindrical samples cut from 125 x 125 x 25mm billets of CMB foam was performed. Sectioning of the billets was undertaken so that samples both longitudinal and transverse to the billet thickness were obtained, thereby enabling detection of any anisotropy in mechanical properties. The samples were 25.3mm in height and 23.3mm in diameter. Compression was carried out on an MTS test frame using three LVDTs placed at equal intervals around the sample, thus accurately measuring the uniformity of the strain on each sample as well as the alignment of the assembly. Testing occurred in position control at 0.18 mm/min with strain data being averaged over all three LVDTs.

2.4 Impulse excitation

Young's modulus was measured by impulse excitation. In this technique, rectangular parallelepipeds are placed such that their flexural nodes of vibration rest on supports at 22% of the length of the bar from either end of the sample. The bar is struck with an elastic tap and the sample's resonant frequency is measured with a handheld transducer or microphone. The frequency, mass and dimensions of the sample can then be used to determine the dynamic Young's modulus of the sample [8].

III. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

3.1 Nanocompression

Nanocompression was attempted on approximately 200 CMB, with a resulting 140 load vs. displacement curves. The remaining 60 CMB compression attempts failed for a variety of reasons, ranging from apparent movement of the CMB between targeting and compression to normal indentation errors. The sole result of nanocompression testing is a load vs. displacement curve for each of the CMB tested. The definitions of several key parameters are labeled in Figure 4. In the figure, the points at which the CMB failed and at which substrate indentation began, denoted by CMB bursts and substrate contact, respectively, determined the definitions of the measured values. The load (P_f) and displacement (δ_f) at failure for each CMB may be extrapolated from the failure point; also, the displacement from the beginning of loading until the indenter tip commences substrate loading must be a measure of the diameter of the CMB. This measure has been termed vertical diameter (ϕ_v). The slope (k) of the loading portion of the curve can be approached as a pseudo-stiffness, akin to the modulus of the material. This is not, however, equal to the modulus because the CMB are hollow spheres. A final useful definition was that of compressive strain at failure:

$$\text{Compressive strain} = \frac{\delta_f}{\phi_v}$$

Figure 4: Nanocompression curve with important failure parameters shown.

The load vs. displacement data collected can be categorized into three distinctive types, based on the curve shape produced: single, imperfect, or nested. For a single CMB, the curve showed a linear load to failure, with one failure point. An imperfect CMB deviated from the single category only in the lack of linearity prior to failure. The nested CMB classification was characterized by multiple failure points, as could be expected from a CMB containing compartments. An example of each category is provided in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Representative nanocompression curves, showing categorization of CMB into single, imperfect, and nested types based on loading behavior.

An important note regarding this figure: the curves provided are illustrative examples of each type of nanocompression, and are not meant to imply that single CMB always have smaller displacements than nested CMB, or vice versa.

Another method of categorizing the CMB, other than through their nanocompressive curve type, has been used. This involved the pre-compression micrographs, which provided a second measure of the CMB diameter, termed the optical diameter (ϕ_o). This diameter has been used in conjunction with the vertical diameter from nanocompression to define the aspect ratio of each CMB.

$$\text{Aspect ratio} = \frac{\phi_o}{\phi_v}$$

The CMB were then classified as either spherical—having an aspect ratio between 0.9 and 1.1—or non-spherical—having aspect ratios less than 0.9 or greater than 1.1.

Both classification schemes have been applied to the CMB population tested. Doing so allowed the elimination of data from CMB that were clearly flawed through either nesting or extreme deviation from spherical morphology. Once this data was removed, the establishment of trends between the CMB loading properties and their physical characteristics was attempted. A relationship was observed between compressive stress at failure and the inverse square root of the vertical diameter of the CMB, as can be seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Compressive strain is proportional to the inverse square root of the CMB diameter.

3.2 Quantitative microscopy of polished CMB foams

These measurements were made on micrographs similar to the one shown previously in Figure 2, which was provided as an example of the structure. Perhaps the greatest gain from these micrographs has not been the measurements taken, but rather direct observation of the microstructure, including broken and compartmentalized CMB. The measurements from Image Pro Plus resulted in a mean lineal intercept of $2.35 \mu\text{m}$. Back-calculation from the mean lineal intercept yielded $1.12 \mu\text{m}$ for the average wall thickness of the CMB. This agrees favorably with the observed values from SEM analysis—as shown in Figure 7—which produced measured values varying from $0.35 \mu\text{m}$ to $2.4 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 7: SEM micrographs showing range in CMB wall thickness

Statistics were considered only for the P_L and A_A values, since those were the measured quantities from quantitative microscopy. The coefficient of variation for the mean linear intercept was 0.05, which is an accepted value for a 95 % confidence interval.

3.3 Mechanical testing

Mechanical property testing of the CMB syntactic foam was performed via unconfined compression testing and impulse excitation. This combination of techniques yielded data on the compressive strength, failure behavior, and modulus of the composites. Samples from two billets of CMB foam were tested in compression, with sample codes indicating the billet in the first three characters and the direction, longitudinal (L) or transverse (T), by the last character. From the compressive tests, the typical result was a stress-strain curve as exemplified in Figure 8. This figure shows the characteristic behavior of foam failure, which was accompanied by audible cracking, followed by flakes spalling from the sample edges. The compressive strength of these composites has been defined as the highest stress attained before the appearance of the first major crack. This value was averaged for the tests in each billet; as Figure 9 demonstrates, there was no significant variation in the strength with either billet or sample orientation.

Figure 8: Typical compression curve.

Figure 9: Range and mean of compressive strengths from unconfined compression of CMB foam.

The overall average compressive strength was 5.6 MPa. From impulse excitation techniques, both Young's and shear moduli were calculated. An average Young's modulus value of 736.9 MPa was measured from 20 samples. The shear modulus was measured at 336.4 MPa from three samples only, since larger samples were necessary for this test and limited material was available.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Efforts to characterize the structure and properties of this carbon microballoon syntactic foam and its constituents are ongoing and have already led to the determination of several important values. The traditional test methods of unconfined compression, impulse excitation, quantitative microscopy, and SEM have produced data on the compressive strength, moduli, and microstructure of these composites. For the CMB foam, the average compressive strength was 5.6 MPa and dynamic modulus values of 737 MPa and 336 MPa were established for the Young's and shear modulus, respectively. Additionally, optical microscopy revealed the foam microstructure to contain broken CMB fragments, and nested CMB. Optical analysis of the foam structure also found the average CMB wall thickness to be 1.12 μm . SEM investigations of the CMB morphology confirmed the irregularities indicated by optical imaging, revealing many large deviations from spherical. In an effort to further characterize the CMB, a new test technique, nanocompression, was developed. Through this technique, a nanoindenter was used to compress individual CMB and record loading and displacement information from each. This was then correlated with the physical characteristics of the CMB, proving that the compressive strain at failure of the CMB was proportional to their diameter.

V. REFERENCES

1. K. Okuno, R.T. Woodhams. **J Cell Plast** 10 (1974) 237-44.
2. C.S. Karthikeyan, S. Sankaran, M.N. Jagdish Kumar, Kishore. **J App Polymer Sci** 81 (2001) 405-411.
3. C. Hiel, D. Dittmann and O. Ishai. **Composite** 24 July (1993) 447-450
4. J. A. DeRuntz Jr. **Journal of Applied Mechanics** 38 no.1, p.23-29
5. E. Bruneton, C. Tallaron, N. Gras-Naulin, A. Cosculluela. **Carbon** 40 (2002) 1919-1927.
6. G.M. Pharr. **Mat Sci & Eng** A253 (1998) 151-159.
7. B.N. Lucas, W.C. Oliver, J.E. Swindeman. **Mat Res Soc Symp Proc** 522 (1998).

8. American Society for Testing and Materials, ATSM Standard E 1876-99, "Standard Test Method for Dynamic Young's Modulus, Shear Modulus, and Poisson's Ration by Impulse Excitation of Vibration," **Annual Book of ASTM Standards**, ASTM, Philadelphia.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by Los Alamos National Laboratory, subcontract #44277-SOL-02 4X. Thanks are due to Struers Applications Lab for assistance with the CMB foam polishing technique.